

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

PHYSICAL CULTURE AS A FACTOR IN PRESERVING THE HEALTH OF STUDENT YOUTH

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Abstract

The article outlines the role of physical education of students and considers the impact of the current situation on the education and lifestyle of students. It has been established that the success of students' mental and cognitive activity depends on their psychophysical state. Methodical advice is offered to improve the physical and psychological state of higher education students in the current situation.

Keywords: physical culture, physical activity, physical activity, health, student youth.

Introduction. Preserving and promoting the health of the younger generation is a strategic task for any state, as it is the youth who embody the future of the nation and determine the further socio-economic development of society. Today, there is a steady trend towards a deterioration in the physical and mental health of young people, including students, due to a number of factors: limited physical activity, information overload, chronic stress, unhealthy lifestyles, etc. Therefore, the search for effective means and methods of strengthening and preserving the health of higher education students is of particular importance. Physical culture as an effective tool is a purposeful motor activity that optimises the physical and psycho-emotional state of a young person. One of the means of physical culture is exercise, which in turn has a beneficial effect on the cardiovascular system, respiratory system, musculoskeletal system and circulatory system. It should be noted that the relevance of this study is that physical culture has been influencing people throughout the history of human society.

The purpose of the article is to analyse the role of physical culture in preserving and strengthening the physical and mental health of modern student youth.

Results and their discussion. The modern educational process in higher education institutions is characterised by a combination of high mental and psycho-emotional stress. Students' learning activities are accompanied by significant emotional and intellectual stress, physical inactivity, stressful situations. Only applicants with good health, high mental and physical performance, and resistance to psycho-emotional stress can successfully implement educational requirements under such conditions [5; 7].

The results of studies [2; 5] show that the restrictions of recent years have led to significant changes in the daily lives of participants in the educational process. Experts note that quarantine has provoked stress in many people due to being in a confined space, constant fear for life and health. In such conditions, both physical and mental health are at risk. Therefore, regular and rationally organised physical exercise is especially important. In the context of distance learning, students' independent activity and ability to work on

themselves are important. The scientific literature constantly emphasises the need to involve students in independent sports activities. Their organisation should ensure optimal motor activity, comprehensive development of functional systems and physical qualities [10].

Physical activity stimulates the production of hormones and neurotransmitters, such as serotonin, dopamine, acetylcholine and norepinephrine, as well as melatonin, which regulates sleep and wakefulness, which is necessary to reduce the negative effects of stress on the body; melatonin production is enhanced, among other things, through regular and systematic physical activity [1]. The regulation of neurochemical balance is the foundation for mental and physical health, which can be achieved through physical activity, which together plays a significant role in the process of combating stress.

Physical culture is an organic part of human culture. It actively affects the vital aspects of the human body, received in the form of dispositions that develop in the course of life under the influence of the environment. Physical culture is based on appropriate motor activity in the form of physical exercises that allow to effectively develop the necessary physical abilities and optimise health.

Physical health includes the level of growth and functioning of the body's organs and systems, their coherence, anthropometric characteristics and adaptive capabilities. According to researchers, it is associated with control over the body and movements, physical endurance, absence of chronic diseases and high performance [8].

Sedentary lifestyles and low levels of physical activity have a negative impact on health, well-being and quality of life, causing additional stress and threatening not only the physical but also the mental health of students. In such a situation, rationally organised physical activity is a factor that helps to maintain inner peace and health, and increases the body's resistance to psycho-emotional stress. Therefore, regular and rationally planned physical exercises are of particular importance during the period of restrictive measures.

The main indicators of physical health are physical development, physical performance, physical norm and physical activity.

The physical development of students affects their academic performance and future career. Due to the large amount of time spent in the classroom, many students develop a sedentary lifestyle, which negatively affects their physical condition and health. Therefore, it is important for students to understand the value of physical activity and a healthy lifestyle, including proper nutrition.

To maintain your physical development, you should regularly engage in sports - fitness, running, swimming, yoga, etc. It is also important to ensure that you eat a healthy diet and get enough exercise. This will help maintain your physical and mental well-being.

Regular exercise and a healthy diet increase physical performance and reduce the risk of developing chronic diseases that can affect your studies.

In addition, a proper level of physical performance improves students' mental health - it helps to reduce stress and increase self-esteem. This improves the quality of life in general and contributes to the achievement of higher results both in education and in other areas.

A healthy physical condition ensures the normal functioning of all body systems and includes indicators of body weight, height, chest volume, as well as the functioning of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, etc. Compliance of physical parameters with the norm has a positive impact on student health. For example, not being overweight and having the right weight-to-height ratio reduces the risk of developing diabetes, cardiovascular disease and other illnesses. Good cardiovascular and respiratory health provides the endurance and energy needed for full-fledged study and life.

Physical activity has many health benefits, including: reducing the risk of developing chronic diseases, improving cardiovascular health, reducing the likelihood of depression and stress, increasing energy, improving mood and overall quality of life.

Students' physical activity has a positive impact not only on their physical health but also on their mental performance. Regular exercise helps to improve blood circulation and oxygenation of the brain, which increases attention, concentration and cognitive function. Exercise also helps reduce stress and improve mood, which has a positive effect on brain function and reduces the risk of depression and anxiety.

Therefore, physical activity is not only good for the body, but also for the mental performance and overall well-being of students. Physical health is a complex concept that encompasses physical, spiritual and social aspects. Their balance is important for maintaining and improving health, quality of life and academic performance.

Health is an invaluable asset for every individual and society. Good health, which is reasonably maintained and strengthened by the individual, can ensure a long and active life. In social life, in the system of education, upbringing and recreation, physical culture reveals its health-improving and general cultural significance. Physical development is closely linked to the

promotion and preservation of human health. Using various physical exercises, a person improves his or her physical condition. The result of physical education activities is physical fitness and the degree of perfection of motor skills [4].

Physical activity contributes to normal growth and development and can help people feel better and reduce the risk of many chronic diseases. Positive health effects occur immediately after exercise, and even short episodes of physical activity are beneficial.

Some of the benefits of physical activity can be achieved immediately, such as reduced anxiety and blood pressure, improved sleep, and some aspects of cognitive function. Other benefits, such as improved cardiorespiratory fitness, increased muscle strength, reduced symptoms of depression, and sustained blood pressure reduction, require several weeks or months of physical activity.

Physically active people cope better with stressful situations, are more cheerful and less prone to mood swings, depression and neurosis.

According to the World Health Organisation, Ukraine ranks first in Europe in terms of the number of mental disorders and people diagnosed with depression, and this figure is growing every year. According to the World Health Organisation, only 40 per cent of students currently belong to the main health group and only about 5 per cent go in for sports on a regular basis. The lack of physical activity among students inevitably leads to disruptions in the functioning of the body's functional systems, which causes negative health conditions that are difficult to avoid later [3].

Since the physical condition of the body is part of the system of cultural values, its perfection and improvement is part of cultural activity. Physical culture is a sphere of activity in which a person reveals his or her natural abilities in terms of physical development and learns the limits of his or her physical potential. Thus, physical culture can be seen as a sphere of realisation of the possibilities that the human body has. Physical culture is seen as a part of personal culture or a part of general culture.

Regular physical activity, rationally incorporated into work and leisure routines, not only promotes health, but also significantly improves performance. However, not all movement exercises performed as part of the home and work process are physical exercises. These can only be movements specially selected to influence various organs and systems, develop physical qualities, and correct physical defects. It has been found that students who systematically engage in sports are physically more developed than their peers who do not play sports [9].

Physical education trains the cardiovascular system and makes it resistant to heavy loads. Physical activity contributes to the development of the musculoskeletal system. Exercise will have a positive effect if certain rules are followed.

During exercise, the human body responds to a given load with reactions. It activates the activity of all organs and systems, which leads to the consumption of energy resources, increases the mobility of nervous processes, strengthens muscles and the bone system.

Thus, the physical fitness of the participants improves, and as a result, a state of the body is achieved when the loads are easily tolerated, and previously unavailable results are the norm for various types of physical activity.

Physical activity can be classified into aerobic, anaerobic and mixed types based on the energy expenditure of the body. During aerobic exercise, the body uses an aerobic, or oxygen, energy supply mechanism. In this case, energy is formed from nutrients (carbohydrates and fats) and the oxygen in the inhaled air is sufficient for their oxidation. Aerobic exercise is the most beneficial for health. They strengthen the cardiovascular, respiratory and other systems of the body. But humans also need anaerobic exercise. Their dosed implementation increases the resistance of tissues to hypoxia (lack of oxygen), the power of the body's enzymatic systems, and increases the supply of energy substances. Usually, when performing various physical exercises, aerobic and anaerobic energy supply mechanisms operate in parallel in the body, with one of them prevailing [11].

During independent physical education, aerobic physical activity should be preferred: running at a calm pace, swimming, cycling, hiking, gymnastic exercises. The main subjective indicator of aerobic exercise is the absence of noticeable shortness of breath during its performance.

Physical activities are divided into training and competitive, specific and non-specific, local, partial and global, by nature - into small, medium, significant (near-borderline), large (borderline), by focus - those that develop individual motor abilities (speed, strength, coordination, endurance, flexibility) or their components (e.g. alactate or lactate anaerobic capabilities, aerobic capabilities), and others.

To achieve the desired training effect, it is not enough to perform only short-term physical exercises. They should be combined with independent activities aimed at improving the body's functional capabilities and developing physical qualities. Only regular and intense training will help you achieve the desired results in physical fitness and health.

The ability to manage one's own mental state, emotions, concentration and attention is an important factor in the effectiveness of student learning. It contributes to emotional balance and mental health. To improve mental performance and normalise the psycho-emotional state, experts advise mastering psychoregulation techniques. The most accessible and widespread of them is autogenic training.

Autogenic training is a method of independently achieving a special (autogenic) state, using it and getting out of it. The term "auto" means "self" and "genos" means "birth". Thus, "autogenic" indicates that the source of the positive effect is the person himself. The word "training" emphasises the need for regular training to achieve results. Thus, autogenous training is a method of achieving a certain health state on your own through regular exercise [6].

Regular physical activity helps to reduce stress, improve mood, increase energy and concentration.

Physical activity is an important component of maintaining mental well-being, as it helps to balance the physical and mental state of a person.

For the effective physical education of students, it is proposed to conduct various types of physical activity: sports competitions and cycling; sports events that will promote physical development and team spirit; promote a healthy lifestyle.

In addition, we offer practical advice on how to improve students' mental health:

meditation helps to reduce stress and anxiety;

Yoga classes relax muscles, reduce stress and improve the ability to concentrate and focus;

regular exercise reduces stress, anxiety and improves mood;

deep breathing reduces stress, increases oxygen levels in the body, concentration and memory.

Physical activity has a multifaceted effect on mental functions, bringing them into an active and stable state.

The most effective ways to recover from fatigue include: performing simple physical exercises; changing the type of activity; proper nutrition, maintaining strict hygiene.

Physical education can include any physical activity, starting with a walk, jogging, performing an elementary set of physical exercises and ending with regular classes in a sports or gym.

Systematic physical training, performing a set of physical exercises during the educational activities of students play an important role as a means of relieving nervous tension and maintaining emotional state.

Exercise or sports increase the level of activity of metabolic processes, train and maintain at a high level the mechanisms responsible for metabolism and energy in the body, and normalise the emotional state of a person.

The role of physical activity is not limited to its health benefits. For people who exercise regularly, regular muscle activity helps to increase the body's mental, intellectual and emotional stability during prolonged strenuous mental or physical work. Optimal physical activity has a positive effect on the psychological state of students.

Students are favourably affected by low and medium physical activity using circular and uniform training methods. This is because the harmonious development of all muscle groups leads to a dynamic manifestation of the processes of excitation and inhibition. Also, the reduction of aggression in those students whose mental tension is directed inward is due to strength and endurance.

To achieve the health benefits of independent sports activities, it is important to plan your physical activity rationally. Properly organised training helps to reduce morbidity, improve physical condition, and increase mental and physical performance. At the same time, if not planned properly, they can have a negative impact. To obtain the best results and a high level of health during independent training, you need to be able to rationally plan the volume and intensity of loads, use self-control techniques.

The introduction of a competence-based approach to physical education should be aimed at developing students' ability to solve life problems through physical education. In particular, the ability to rationally plan one's own motor activity, use physical education means to improve health, increase functional capabilities, correct performance, and regulate psycho-emotional state. To solve this problem, teachers should pay more attention to improving the theoretical and methodological training of students. It is the formation of knowledge in the field of physical culture and the skills of their application that will contribute to the formation of health competences of future professionals.

Conclusions. Therefore, physical education should become an integral part of everyone's life, including students. It helps not only to maintain physical fitness but also to maintain mental health at the proper level. Therefore, it is important to continue to develop the system of physical education for young people and promote a healthy and active lifestyle. At the same time, excessive physical and psychological stress has a negative impact on health and well-being. Although intense training is beneficial, too much exercise can cause injury or exhaustion. That's why it's important to follow a proper daily routine, plan your workload rationally, and take time to rest and recover.

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